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MESO SPACE REPRESENTATION BY CHILDREN IN THE 1ST YEAR OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL: AN EXPERIENCE IN THE CLASSROOM

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ABSTRACT:

This report seeks to present observations and reflections that discuss a Geometry activity in a class of the 1st year of Elementary School in a school in the Municipal Network of São Paulo. For this, the studies by Rainiere and Colombo (2012) were used as a theoretical reference. The theme Spatial Relations is presented in the Common Curricular Base - BNCC (2017) in the unit called "Geometry", which defines for the 1st year the Object of Knowledge: "location of objects and people in space, using different reference points and vocabulary". The narrative presents an approach of reflection on the practice itself, based on the methodological and didactic propositions of the authors Rainiere and Colombo (2012). The activity was configured as an important path for learning spatial relationships and was identified in the students. an evolution in understanding the language needed to communicate the position or path of an object or person.